

FICTION AND SOCIAL SITUATION

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ANNOTATION

Socialist Labor was even a means of protecting the social position of people and the achievements of the revolution, strengthening the economic foundation of the young Soviet republic, organizing a socialist competition. In particular, "who will beat whom?" the basis of the slogan was socialist labor. During the Great Patriotic War, labor and patriotism became an integral concept.

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The example of a boiler in which life boils is in constant motion and change. The total processes taking place in it are considered the main topic of literature. The difference between the creator and ordinary people is that he sees, analyzes the surrounding reality through the eyes of artistry. Whether it's the novelty that is happening in society, the rise or the shortcomings that are happening creative writer is influenced by it and it's impossible to stop working again. He artistically presents the horrors that are going on in his dreams to the public. It is known that in the literature of all peoples, many works have been written about the past and famous historical martyrs. In particular, there are also works on this topic in Uzbek literature of the 20th century. In these works, The Breath of a certain period left its seal to one degree or another. As it turns out, we directly get acquainted with the atmosphere, circumstances of the era in which the work was created through the work. If you want to get acquainted with the original way and environment of society, then of course it is necessary to observe the common population and its way of life. How the environment

is reflected in the fact that they are in their ordinary life. That is why the main subject and hero of almost the entire sample of fiction is considered either an ordinary laborer or a villager. Even in fact, the original state of the boiling pot is known from its bottom. Even in all types of examples of long-period fiction, the hero who shows courage will be from an ordinary laborer.

It is known that the 60s and 70s were a period when confidence in socialist ideas was “revived” in society. That is, all the problems in the life of society were caused by the consequences of cult of personality, and now in many people there was a belief that “the policy of our party government is on the right track, a communist society will be built in the near future.” Given that Pirimkul Kadyrov, who created in the 60s and 70s, entered literature at the end of the 50s, this belief forms the basis of his social views. Therefore, the heroes of the works created by this generation are men of struggle, the leader of external behavior in their interpretation. After all, these heroes live with that idea, that purpose, fight. In the works of this period lies the struggle between those who live for that purpose and give halal to reach it.

Thanks to Labor, a person not only changes things in nature, but also matures himself, his mental and physical abilities grow. In the process of Labor, man subordinates the forces of nature to his goal. We can see this in the image of the heroine of the story” Heritage " Yolqin. When choosing him as an ordinary country man, a child of a kamharj family, the writer also refers to the state of the era. Yolqin made great strides, although he was not a suitor who would lean on him. So, in the conquest of any peak, only a person must rely on his labor. Such an idea was a desirable theme for the politics of the period. On the basis of communist ideas, literature was used to attract a person only to work. Works of this type and idea became the need for the era. And we will not be mistaken if we say that the story” heritage " is a perfect work created in response.

Each national literature is distinguished from the literature of other peoples, first of all by its national traditions, the nationality of its heroes, the uniqueness of the described life. In this sense, the works of Uzbek writers should also be emboldened by

the Uzbek spirit, the Uzbek way of life, the Uzbek character and the themes and ideas that are important to Uzbekistan.

There is an evolutionary history of the artistic reflection of the theme of labor in Uzbek Soviet literature. In the 20s and 30s, reading and working constituted the most important ideals of the people of socialism. Socialist Labor was even a means of protecting the social position of people and the achievements of the revolution, strengthening the economic foundation of the young Soviet republic, organizing a socialist competition. In particular, "who will beat whom?" the basis of the slogan was socialist labor. During the Great Patriotic War, labor and patriotism became an integral concept. Labor and its productive derivative became the focus of German fascism. The post-war years became the main topic of our literature—a man of Labor and labor. The spiritual image of a Soviet person is revealed in the process of Labor and its active attitude to Labor. Now the concept of Labor and the Soviet person has become an integral unit. Labor—material of people of a developed socialist society not only makes up the Soviet lifestyle. The Communist attitude towards Labor, becoming a Communist labor forger, increasing labor productivity and searching for new resources have become factors that determine the lifestyle of a Soviet person. Soviet literature in its daily activities covers these problems from the point of view of principal partiality and high volatility, standing close to the spirituality of every Soviet person who is becoming a person of active activity in society, decorating his marriage and making his work enjoyable.

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